

RESEARCH ON OPTIMISING METHODS FOR COMBATING CYANOBACTERIA IN FISH PONDS

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Abstract

Cyanobacterial blooms are a major problem for aquatic ecosystems and fish farming activities, affecting water quality and the health of organisms. This paper compares the effectiveness of three control methods applied in experimental fish ponds: chemical treatment with copper sulphate, treatment with hydrogen peroxide, and an ecological method based on the use of barley straw. Over a period of eight weeks (June-August 2025), the physical and chemical indicators of the water, the concentration of chlorophyll a, and the density of cyanobacteria were analysed in four ponds with a history of algal blooms, namely cyanobacteria. The results show that hydrogen peroxide (5 mg/l) significantly reduced cyanobacterial biomass ($p < 0.05$) without major negative effects on other parameters, while copper sulphate had a rapid but temporary effect. Barley straw showed moderate effectiveness, with slow but favorable effects on maintaining ecological balance.

Introduction

Cyanobacteria (*Microcystis*, *Dolichospermum/Anabaena*, *Planktothrix*, *Aphanizomenon*, etc.) cause frequent blooms in freshwater basins, with negative effects on fish farming, affecting water quality (turbidity, hypoxia, taste/smell, hepatotoxic/neurotoxic toxins) with effects on biodiversity and fish productivity [1]. These photosynthetic microorganisms produce hepatotoxic and neurotoxic toxins (microcystins, anatoxins), reduce dissolved oxygen, and promote eutrophication (Anderson et al., 2023).

Control measures are divided into preventive (nutrient reduction) and reactive (chemical algicides, biocontrol, physical methods). In the context of fish farming, the choice of method must balance effectiveness, cost, risks to fish, and residues in water/products [2].

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and other species. The use of barley straw produces inhibitory compounds that, under certain conditions, reduce algal growth. Its effectiveness is slow and variable, but relatively safe from an ecological point of view. Copper sulphate is effective but toxic to invertebrates (zooplankton) and can lead to the rapid return of algal blooms.

Materials and methods

The experiment was conducted at the Research and Development Station for Fisheries Nucet in 2025, between June and August. Four fish ponds with a history of cyanobacterial blooms (B1-B4) were used, with an average depth of 1.5 m, and with a surface of 1000 m²/pond (Figure 1).

The treatments applied were:

B1-control (no treatment);

B2 chemical treatment with copper sulphate (CuSO₄) 0.4 mg/l, weekly application, solution dissolved and dispersed on the surface of the pond;

B3-treatment with hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) 5 mg/l applied every two months);

B4-ecological treatment with barley straw (50 g/m²), distributed evenly over the entire pond before flooding.

The physical and chemical quality parameters of the water (pH, dissolved oxygen, transparency, ammoniacal nitrogen, nitrates, phosphates), chlorophyll a, and cyanobacteria density were measured and analyzed weekly.

Water samples were taken from the surface layer (0-0.5m), aiming to be collected from approximately the same location for each basin.

Equipment used for determining: Multiparameter (DO; pH; conductivity; ammonium; nitrates), JENWAI 7200 spectrophotometer, Jenway 6320D spectrophotometer, Axio Vert 1 ZEISS compact inverted microscope, Secchi disc, planktonic net.

Samples were taken from the surface layer (0-50 cm), stored at 4°C, and analysed within a maximum of 6 hours.

Data analysis:

The data were processed in Microsoft Excel 365.

Correlations: Pearson coefficient between parameters ($p < 0.05$).

Figure 1. Basins used in the experiment

Results and Discussions:

Physicochemical parameters analysed

pH

pH values showed significant variations depending on the treatment and the experimental period. In the control basin (B1), the pH decreased steadily from 7.65 to 6.95, reflecting the accumulation of organic substances and the intensification of microbial respiration processes. In the CuSO₄-treated basin (B2), values ranged from 7.55 to 6.80, confirming the marked acidification induced by the treatment and the ionic imbalances resulting from cell lysis. In contrast, the eco-technological basins maintained better chemical stability: in B3 (H₂O₂), the pH ranged between 7.80 and 7.35, and in B4 (barley straw) between 7.70 and 7.28, the values being statistically significantly more stable ($p < 0.05$) compared to the CuSO₄-treated basin (Figure 2).

Figure 2. pH recorded during the experimental period

Dissolved oxygen

Dissolved oxygen (O₂) showed a trend directly related to photosynthesis intensity and algal bloom severity. In B1, values ranged between 5.2 and 6.8 mg/l, with a downward trend in recent weeks, indicating trophic stress. In B2, treatment with CuSO₄ initially caused an increase (7.0 mg/l), followed by a rapid decrease to 4.8 mg/l, due to the decomposition of dead biomass. In B3, oxygen remained constant (7.5-8.3 mg/l), and in B4 it gradually increased from 7.0 to 8.0 mg/l, indicating moderate photosynthetic activity and stable redox balance. Comparatively, the average dissolved oxygen values were 20-25% higher in the eco-technological basins than in the chemically treated ones (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Dissolved oxygen recorded during the experimental period

Transparency

Water transparency, determined using the Secchi disc, varied inversely with cyanobacterial density and nutrient concentrations. In B1, transparency gradually decreased from 42 cm to 25 cm as algal growth intensified. In B2, after the application of CuSO_4 , transparency increased sharply to 60 cm, but subsequently decreased to 35 cm, indicating the reappearance of phytoplankton after the reactivation of nutrients released by lysis. In B3, values remained high (68-85 cm), and in B4, they stabilised between 70 and 80 cm, demonstrating significantly higher water clarity in ecotechnologically treated basins. The differences between the basins are statistically significant ($p < 0.01$), and the correlation coefficient between transparency and chlorophyll a is negative ($r = -0.88$), confirming the inverse relationship between phytoplankton biomass and water clarity (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Transparency during the experimental period
Nutrient concentrations (NH_4^+ and PO_4^{3-})

Ammonium concentration (NH_4^+)

Evolution of ammonium (NH_4^+) concentrations reflected the intensity of mineralisation processes and the efficiency of the treatments applied. In B1, the values increased steadily (0.70-1.72 mg/l), indicating the accumulation of organic degradation products. In B2 (treated with $CuSO_4$), there was a sharp increase to 1.85 mg/l (week 3), followed by a slow decrease associated with subsequent nitrification processes. In B3, NH_4^+ decreased steadily (0.65 - 0.32 mg/l) due to oxidation under the action of H_2O_2 , and in B4 it decreased slowly but steadily (0.60 - 0.38 mg/l). The average reduction in ammonium was 75% in B3 and 55% in B4, and only 25% in B2 (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Evolution of ammonium (NH_4^+) concentrations during the experimental period

Phosphate concentration (PO_4^{3-})

Phosphates (PO_4^{3-}) (Figure 6) showed a similar trend to ammonium. In B1, levels increased from 0.18 to 0.41 mg/l, and in B2 they peaked at 0.45 mg/l in week 3, followed by a gradual decline. In B3 and B4, values decreased steadily to 0.06 mg/l, confirming the role of eco-technologies in reducing phosphorus availability.

Figure 6. Evolution of phosphate concentrations (PO_4^{3-}) during the experimental period

Evolution of cyanobacterial biomass

Hydrobiological determinations showed consistent variations in phytoplankton biomass, dominated by the genera *Microcystis*, *Anabaena*, and *Aphanizomenon*.

During the experimental period, significant variations in biomass were observed between the four basins.

In the control basin (B1), biomass increased steadily from $5,2 \times 10^4$ to $2,6 \times 10^5$ cells/ml, reflecting progressive eutrophication and favourable conditions for bloom formation. In the $CuSO_4$ -treated basin (B2), an initial reduction was followed by a partial recovery (from 5.1×10^4 to 8.0×10^4 cells/ml), indicating temporary chemical suppression and subsequent recolonisation after nutrient reactivation.

In the H_2O_2 -treated basin (B3), biomass decreased sharply (5.5×10^4 to 8.0×10^3 cells/ml), confirming strong oxidative inhibition of cyanobacteria without secondary pollution.

The barley straw basin (B4) showed a gradual decline (5.0×10^4 to 1.5×10^4 cells/ml), consistent with the slow release of phenolic compounds that inhibit algal photosynthesis (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Evolution of cyanobacterial biomass in the basins analysed during the experimental period

Evolution of chlorophyll a concentration

The experimental data revealed clear differences depending on the treatment:

B1 (control) showed a continuous increase in chlorophyll a (28-92 $\mu\text{g/l}$), indicating progressive eutrophication and dense proliferation of cyanobacteria.

B2 (CuSO_4) showed a transient reduction followed by pigment recovery (27-31 $\mu\text{g/l}$), confirming the short-term impact of chemical control.

B3 (H_2O_2) showed a sharp decline (29-8 $\mu\text{g/l}$), highlighting a sustained inhibition of pigment synthesis and cellular activity.

B4 (barley straw) showed a moderate, steady decrease (26-10 $\mu\text{g/l}$), linked to the gradual release of natural algicidal substances (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Evolution of chlorophyll a concentration in the basins analysed during the experimental

Pearson Correlation Coefficients

Strong positive correlations were observed between cyanobacterial biomass and chlorophyll a concentration across all basins ($r > 0.87$, $p < 0.05$), confirming the direct dependence between cellular density and pigment content. In eco-technological basins (B3 and B4), nutrient levels (NH_4^+ , PO_4^{3-}) declined steadily in parallel with biomass and chlorophyll-a, yielding very high correlations ($r > 0.94$, $p < 0.01$). The CuSO_4 -treated basin (B2) displayed weaker relationships ($r = 0.7$), consistent with temporary algicidal effects and subsequent nutrient release.

Overall, nutrient availability exerted a strong regulatory control on cyanobacterial proliferation and pigment synthesis, demonstrating the efficiency of eco-technological management approaches in maintaining ecological stability.

Table 1. Pearson Correlation Coefficients (r, p < 0.05)

Basin	Biomass–Chl-a	Biomass–NH ₄ ⁺	Biomass–PO ₄ ³⁻	Chl-a – NH ₄ ⁺	Chl-a–PO ₄ ³⁻
B1	0.987	0.962	0.953	0.949	0.938
B2	0.876	0.741	0.702	0.678	0.642
B3	0.991	0.955	0.947	0.931	0.926
B4	0.984	0.942	0.936	0.915	0.904

Conclusions

The research results confirm the effectiveness of eco-technological methods in controlling cyanobacteria and stabilising aquatic fish ecosystems. Treatment with hydrogen peroxide ensured a 70-80% reduction in ammonia and phosphate compounds, without ecotoxic impact, while barley straw provided a slow but stable effect. The CuSO₄-based chemical method caused strong fluctuations in parameters and secondary nutrient releases, which limit its long-term applicability. Ecotechnological methods are a priority for the sustainable management of fish waters affected by cyanobacterial blooms.

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